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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Implications of Student 's Online Learning Experience on Social and Emotional Behavior

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the implications of students' online learning experiences on social and emotional behavior in Akidah Akhlak subjects at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Hidayatullah Temanggung Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study uses a qualitative descriptive design with the type of field research. Data were obtained from students who took part in Akidah Akhlak learning. The method used is interviews, observation and documentation, then reduced, presented and analyzed. The results of this study indicate that online learning has an impact on social and emotional behavior including students being less cooperative because they rarely play together, lack tolerance, lack of socializing with friends, limited learning at home, children's emotions sometimes feel bored and sad.

Keywords: Student Experience, Online Learning

Introduction

The temporary closure of educational institutions as an effort to contain the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on changing face-to-face learning to online learning (Esteban M. Aucejo, 2020). These changes resulted in learning problems among students. Problems that arise due to the lack of student learning experience before the implementation of online learning. So students are forced to study online with very minimal conditions, both preparation, tools and online learning experiences for students during the Covid-19 period (Nopa Yusnilita, 2020).

The global Covid-19 pandemic has created a gripping and truly unprecedented situation and it is unknown when this will end (Maila DH Raheem, 2020) . Covid-19 has dramatically changed the world of education globally. Millions of students were affected by the closure of their educational institutions, which resulted in the largest online learning movement in the history of education. With the sudden change from face-to-face learning to distance learning (Ghada Refaat El Said, 2021) . Not to mention students who are forced to maintain distance, self-quarantine, self-isolation, stay at home, and travel restrictions. (Mahiswaran Selvanathan, 2020) . Given the direct effects of COVID-19 in many places, another question highlights the possibility of still meeting the sustainable development goals (SDGs) by 2030. This is definitely the online learning experience of most students in Indonesia (Afip Miftahul Basar, 2020) .

The continuity of distance online education depends on students' experience in participating in online learning (Liyan Song and Janette R. Hill, 2007) . The online learning experience during the Covid 19 era is a picture of what students and teachers do and how they understand what they are actually doing (Azmil Abidah, 2020) . It is also used as an explanatory factor for what teachers and students do based on their

experiences (Clandinin J, 1998). This learning is an educational innovation to answer the challenge of the availability of varied learning resources (Putri 2022).

Learning experience is a series of student activities carried out to obtain information and competencies in accordance with the goals to be achieved (Megawati, 2018). The learning experience will not be separated from a person's learning process (Efriana 2021). Because the learning experience will make it easier for someone to understand the lesson or knowledge to be learned and can affect learning outcomes (Khoirunnisaa and Surabaya 2022). The experience that has been owned will be used at the final stage of learning, namely the exam. So the better the learning experience will have good implications for individual achievement (Anggita Gardessna Sari, 2018).

There are two main things that make research on online learning experiences so important. First, the unprecedented global health crisis of COVID-19 has killed more than a million people worldwide. People's concerns about the many unknowns what the Corona virus brings continues to spread and permeate everyday life. Second, the global education sector has undergone drastic changes as institutions are forced to develop and implement new systems that allow the teaching and learning process to be fully conducted online in a relatively short time (Nathanson, 2020). Teachers and students seem to have no choice even though they may not be ready for change. Therefore, the researchers speculated that the stress caused by the wider environment and the rapid shift from traditional classrooms to online classes could have a negative impact on the learning and teaching experiences of teachers and students during the pandemic.

However, if all activities are only carried out at home, it will cause psychosomatic effects, namely physical disturbances caused by psychological factors and emotional piles that can cause shocks to a person in society, such as anxiety, stress, influencing social environment. a lot of negative thoughts, such as because of hoax news and so on (Azizah Nurul Fadlilah, 2020). This context includes family, peers, school, and the surrounding environment, where the most direct interaction occurs with social people, for example with parents, teachers, and peers.

It's hard to deny that during the implementation of online learning this has happened interactions between teachers and students. Although the Minister of Research, Technology and Higher Education said that the online platform was able to support interaction between the community of students and teachers at various levels (Menristek Dikti 2022), this disorder This causes the absorption of knowledge not as if it was done offline (Anna Sun and Xiufang Chen, 2016). The limitations of internet infrastructure and devices owned by teachers and students are very diverse in their abilities, this is also the cause of the limited online learning and the perceived obstacles that are quite a lot. Wening Sekar Kusuma, 2020).

Students were also found to be less prepared to face the online learning series. Aucejo, 2020) and the low ability of students in the use of online learning technology (Shivangi Dhawan, 2020). Students also feel alienated from online learning because they cannot meet friends at madrasas as before online learning was carried out, this shows that students actually realize that social relationships are very important to support their learning (Forest Hamid, 2020). Because so far they feel they communicate more with machines than humans (Janet WH Sit, 2005).

Another thing that makes me sad is the low quality of learning, especially learning Morals. Starting from students who do not use standard words and polite language, and sometimes there are also those who use young people's slang which maybe the teacher himself does not understand what the word means. Not to mention the students did not see the right time to contact the teacher and did not even ask for permission first when they wanted to make a call or video call. Not a few students who consider this as a matter of course.

Online learning activities are carried out at all levels of education, so learning Akidah Akhlak at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Hidayatullah Temanggung Indonesia must also be done online. Akidah Akhlak learning takes place by utilizing various platforms according to learning needs, including: Zoom, Google classroom, Whatsapp, telegram and Youtube Video (Catrin Sohrabi, 2020). However, the Akhlak Akidah lessons are presented by the teacher in the form of tasks with minimal, comprehensive and in-depth explanations. Along with that, the knowledge and information that students learn from each subject matter received is limited and of poor quality. (Muassomah, 2021).

Even though Akidah Akhlak learning is done online, it does not mean that the teacher will not decrease or lose his role. (Umi Muzayanah, 2020). Indeed, there are some teacher roles that have not been able to run optimally, such as the parenting role due to distance. Here, teachers need to involve parents as the

vanguard to accompany their children to study at home. Because after all, parents still have to guide and teach their children to always respect the Master. At least the teacher gives direction to students to always be polite and ethical in this online learning process. Teach students about how to be ethical and polite to teachers, especially in terms of communicating online (Regiani Abidin, 2020).

This is important because being ethical to teachers is part of the cultivation of commendable morals in Akidah Akhlak. The efforts of teachers and parents in instilling the values of faith and piety, noble character, noble character and discipline, hard work, responsibility will not succeed if there is no direct or indirect family involvement. Nurul Fatiha, 2020).

In fact, online learning is more or less as effective as traditional classroom learning (Pearl Jacobs, 2013). Smaldino, Lowther, and Russell revealed that online learning is able to realize an effective learning function (Robert Heinich, 2012). Pros and cons are common among many people. No need to worry too much, if learning is designed and implemented well, students will learn better and produce good results as well.

According to research conducted by Learning House, Inc. (B. Aslanian Carol, 2013), showed that 85% of students who took face-to-face and online learning felt that they had the same and better experience in learning for face-to-face programs and 37% felt that learning online is more of an experience. Stern explained that online learning is learning that takes place through the internet (Joshua Stern, 2004). However, online learning is only one type of distance learning, a general term for learning that is not in traditional classrooms (Henny Yulia, 2020).

Learning Morals and Faith during the Covid 19 period which was carried out online is certainly expected to have a positive impact on students and teachers (Paul Chilton, 2010). Students' responses or perceptions are important to learn and it is important to know more deeply because students' perceptions describe stimuli, follow-ups, and learning experiences that can support students in realizing the achievement of learning goals (Lestari, 2021).

The purpose of this study then was to find out the online learning experience of students in Akidah Akhlak subjects during the Covid 19 period at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Hidayatullah Temanggung Indonesia through a synthesis of existing evidence. In particular, the authors plan to achieve the objectives by considering the implications for the social and emotional behavior of students.

Implications for Student Social Behavior

a. Attitude of Students Less Cooperative

This decrease in cooperative attitudes in students occurs because during online learning children cannot carry out social interactions with friends and other people (Massie and Nababan 2021). This was revealed based on interviews with parents of students who stated that when asked to complete assignments, their children always complained of difficulties, some of them even preferred to play on their cellphones or watch YouTube rather than study with parental guidance.

When this data is confirmed to the student concerned. The student agreed and stated that he preferred watching YouTube to learning online about Akidah Akhlak. The researcher gave follow-up questions and the students said that learning aqidah was boring, because there were a lot of arguments to be learned while students could not read Arabic well.

In the process of learning at home during this pandemic, children experience a lack of cooperative attitudes which are usually trained at school, cooperative attitudes in children are slightly reduced. Students are also disturbed in their social development in several aspects, such as being less able to accept diversity and low tolerance for others. Rezka Arina Rahma, 2018).

b. Less Socialized Students

Also found are data related to behavior during online learning of Akidah Akhlak at home. Such as grammar, association, dressing, eating and so on are far from ideal for someone who has studied morals. Data from students' parents, Mrs. Yuliati said, "I feel that my child in this pandemic period, where everything has to be done at home, even to play with friends, is not allowed, right because at times like this, now I am a quieter child than I am. usually". Then Mrs. Lina Setyowati: When I got an assignment from the teacher to make a video of memorizing prayers, etiquette reading the Qur'an, my child always didn't believe

in himself and said he was ashamed. Mrs. Hamawiyah: ... at times like this my child rarely saw his friends, once met briefly with his friends they looked awkward.

Socialization is the process of learning the roles, status and values needed to participate in social institutions. Socialization is the process by which an individual learns and internalizes norms and values throughout his life in the society in which he belongs and builds his social identity.

In the learning process at home, students cannot meet their classmates, so they experience a lack of socializing with people around them or their peers. Social development is the development of behavior in children where children are asked to adjust to the rules that apply in society. In other words, social development is a child's learning process in adjusting to the norms, morals, and traditions of a group (Malik F, Marwaha R 2022). Social development refers to a child's ability to: have knowledge in managing and fully express emotions, both positive and negative emotions, be able to establish relationships with other children and adults around them, and actively explore the environment through learning.

Children's social development is obtained from maturity and learning opportunities from various environmental responses to children. Optimal social development is obtained from healthy social responses and opportunities given to children to develop a positive self-concept. Through play activities, children can develop their interests and attitudes towards others. Likewise, activities that are too much dominated by the teacher will hinder the social development of children. This decline in the achievement of social development can occur because while online, children cannot interact socially with other people, especially teachers and friends (Hesti Wulandari, 2020).

c. Non-Independent Students

Another surprising finding is that most of the tasks assigned by Akidah Akhlak teachers are assisted or even carried out by parents. One of them has the initials Mr. MH: ...in learning faith, I help my child learn, sometimes I myself am still impatient with it, I am still often annoyed if it is not easy to understand...it is very difficult to learn Faith material if you have to go online.... When this data was confirmed to the student, the student said the same thing :it's difficult to learn Akidah Akhlak online, I don't understand that's why my mother helped me with assignments.

The results of the above study indicate that students have a rather low level of learning independence. The reason is, not all students are familiar with online learning (Agus Purwanto, 2020). Students do not yet have a distance learning culture because so far the learning system has been carried out face-to-face, in Indonesia the use of e-learning is still slow, in contrast to developed countries outside which have used e-learning at a more advanced stage (Dede Rahmat Hidayat, 2020). The supporting foundation as a support for e-learning learning was also found to have several shortcomings, for example one teacher said that when he used the internet to browse learning material sources, it was seen that the internet access owned by the school was sometimes still slow or slow and not all spots were in it. internet wifi coverage (Survey Study from Home – Ministry of Education and Culture 2021).

Implications for Students' Emotional Behavior

a. Students Feel Bored and Tired

Another finding from this study, it was found that students feel bored if they are constantly at home. This of course has an impact on the emotions of these students. The implementation of the home study policy made some students feel anxious and depressed.

A student guardian named Mrs. Hamidah said "every time I take my child to study or do assignments, my child always complains and feels bored" Mrs. Tarwiyati also said that during the interview "my child doesn't seem enthusiastic about learning... she wants to meet her friends and study there..." . Another thing said by Mrs. Tri Palupi "...there is my child's behavior when he is tired of studying, he even plays with the cat...".

This monotonous and uninteresting situation will certainly cause boredom. Boredom is a condition that is often experienced by everyone, especially students who are still in class VII of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Hidayatullah Temanggung Indonesia, especially in a state full of anxiety like today. Emotions that arise in children also depend on how parents or those around them support how learning occurs at home (Katherine Drane, 2020). The impact of boredom for each child is different depending on how the child responds to and handles this boredom

b. Students Miss Friends and Teachers

The teacher is a guide for students in the process of socializing and teaching various kinds of knowledge that students do not yet have at home. However, the pandemic forced students and teachers to separate in carrying out teaching and learning activities. This has an impact on students who miss and want to meet their teachers and friends. Some informants said:

Ilma Anisa Ulatifa: ... I miss my classmate , because he often brings snacks

Ahmad Rifianto :... it's better to learn to meet the teacher, you can kiss hands...

Silvi Amalia :... I really want to go to school soon, I really miss being with my friends ..

These results indicate that when students feel stressed and bored studying online for a long time at home and miss their friends and teachers. Overcoming this requires parental participation to help students provide internal encouragement and reinforcement. If students have started to build reinforcement in themselves according to the learning task that is being carried out, it will have a significant impact on the students themselves (Subarto, 2020).

Conclusion

Online learning experiences greatly affect the social and emotional behavior of students. The results of this study indicate that online learning has an impact on social and emotional behavior including students who are less cooperative because they rarely play together, lack tolerance, lack of socializing with friends, limited learning at home, children's emotions sometimes feel bored and sad, children feel homesick. friends and teachers. The results of this study can be used as a reference for evaluating the implementation of online learning or learning from home, considering that online learning will continue.

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